

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 6

National Observatory of Athens

© 2024

FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

Project start date: 01.11.2020

Project end date: 31.07.2024

Budget: 163,701 €

The FLAME research project was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) under the “2nd Call for HFRI Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Number: 00559).

H.F.R.I.
Hellenic Foundation for
Research & Innovation

Deliverable Information

Deliverable number and name	D5.3 e-Newsletter Issue 6
Due date	30.11.2023
Delivery date	31.07.2024
Related work package	WP5 Dissemination
Author(s)	T.M. Giannaros, G. Papavasileiou
Approved by	T.M. Giannaros
Dissemination level	Public
Version	0.1 (31.07.2024)

Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 6** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

During the period from July 2023 to August 2024, we continued advancing fire weather research in Greece and Europe. Within this period, we published two papers in international scientific journals, one about the critical fire weather patterns of Greece and the other about fire weather extremes in Europe. We also completed the analysis of synoptic and sub-synoptic dynamics of fire weather by studying selected past wildfire events. Further, we moved on with developing a wind gust parameterization of the coupled fire-atmosphere WRF-SFIRE modeling system. Last but not least, we compiled a Policy Brief that translates the knowledge gained through the FLAME project to practical recommendations for improving wildfire management in Greece.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
31.07.2024

PARTICIPATION IN WORKSHOP TARGETTING MEGAFIRES

Between Saturday 25 May and Saturday 1 June, 2024, we visited San José (California, USA) for a research collaboration with Craig Clements' team at the Wildfire Interdisciplinary Research Center. During our visit so far, we have had the unique opportunity to:

- 🔥 Visit areas affected by major wildfires
- 🔥 See up close the mobile meteorological radar used for gathering valuable measurements directly from the fire field
- 🔥 Visit remote fire-weather monitoring stations

We also participated in a Technical Meeting (Workshop) focused on planning a field campaign to collect measurements from extreme wildfires and megafires. On the first day of the Workshop, we had the opportunity to present to our American colleagues the corresponding steps we are taking in Europe, with a special focus on Greece. Discussions with top experts from the USA serve as both inspiration and fuel for further advancing our understanding of extreme wildfires and megafires, with the ultimate goal of strengthening our resilience.

PRESENTING FLAME AT THE ANNUAL WEATHER AND CLIMATE CONFERENCE 2024

From Monday, July 8 to Wednesday, July 10, 2024, our team member Dr. George Papavasileiou was in Reading, UK, to present the results of the FLAME research project at the Royal Meteorological Society's Annual Weather and Climate Conference 2024.

George's presentation, photo highlights of which are shown below, focused on the new wildfire reality that we are now facing in Greece and around the world, with references to the tools and knowledge developed within the framework of the FLAME research project. The audience showed great interest, and it was recognized that there is a growing need to capitalize on the

knowledge and tools of the meteorological community to enhance our preparedness for present and future wildfires.

UCPM EVALUATION REPORT FOR GREECE MADE PUBLIC

🇪🇺 The Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) has released the report from an independent team of experts, requested by the Greek Government and delivered to it, regarding the management of wildfires in our country. Among the many significant recommendations included in this report, the following stand out:

🔥 The need to update the fire danger prediction map, which dates back to 1980. Although considered outdated, this map continues to be a source of information for strategic planning of wildfire risk management measures. [p. 27 of the report]

🔥 Development of a comprehensive wildfire risk assessment in collaboration between the research and academic communities and public agencies. Special emphasis should be placed on wildland-urban interface zones. [p. 27 of the report]

🔥 Adaptation of the concept of the fire season, based on monitoring meteorological conditions, drought occurrence, and vegetation stress, to enhance preparedness. [p. 30 of the report]

🔥 Designation and use of tactical maps and fire behavior analysis maps to improve response efforts. [p. 31 of the report]

🔥 A clear need for better understanding of wildfire causes. [p. 31 of the report]

🔥 Collection, analysis, evaluation, and exchange of information and data on the actual causes of fire outbreaks. [p. 31 of the report]

🔥 Establishment of an official process for deriving lessons learned after each fire season. [p. 32 of the report]

The full text of the report, which includes an extensive summary in Greek, is available [here](#).

FLAME PUBLICITY FACTS

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

1. Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM (2024) Synoptic-scale drivers of fire weather in Greece. *Science of the Total Environment* 925, 171715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171715>.

2. Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G (2023) Changes in European fire weather extremes and related atmospheric drivers. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 342, 109749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2023.109749>.

Conference posters and presentations

1. Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM (2023) The predictability of the synoptic-scale fire weather conditions during the 2018 Mati wildfire. *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Meteorology, Climatology and Atmospheric Physics (COMECAP 2023)*, 25 – 29 September 2023, Athens, Greece. <https://doi.org/10.3390/envirosciproc2023026164>.

2. Papavasileiou G (2024) Increasing awareness and preparedness for extreme fire weather and behavior. *RMetS Annual Weather and Climate Conference 2024*, 8 – 10 July 2024, Reading, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13152545>.

3. Giannaros TM (2024) Empowering prevention in Europe and Greece through an advanced fire weather information and early warning system. *2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 7 – 12 July 2024, Athens, Greece. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13162213>.

4. Giannaros TM (2023) Climatology, trends, and atmospheric drivers of fire weather extremes in Europe. *Annual Meeting of the Mediterranean Geosciences Union 2023*, 26 – 30 November 2023, Istanbul, Türkiye. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13162655>.

5. Papavasileiou G (2023) Forecasting Eastern Mediterranean fire weather conditions in the medium-range. *Annual Meeting of the Mediterranean Geosciences Union 2023*, 26 – 30 November 2023, Istanbul, Türkiye.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13171668>.

6. Papavasileiou G (2023) The predictability of the synoptic-scale fire weather conditions during the 2018 Mati wildfire. 16th International Conference on Meteorology, Climatology and Atmospheric Physics (COMECAP 2023), 25 – 29 September 2023, Athens, Greece.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13184165>.

FLAME in the media

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/563062315/i-machi-tis-tithaseysis-ton-mega-pyrkagion/>

<https://www.news247.gr/magazine/reportage/stin-ellada-kinigame-kai-tis-foties-anti-na-tis-svinoume/>

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/world/563153134/pyrkagia-stin-kalifornia-mechri-kai-o-oros-megafire-einai-ligos/>

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/life/environment/562978456/o-aprilios-thymizei-ioynio-kai-apeilei-me-nees-pyrkagies/>

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 6

Dr. T.M. **Giannaros**, Fire Meteorologist, Senior Researcher, IERSD/NOA

Dr. G. Papavasileiou, Meteorologist, Post-doctoral Researcher, IERSD/NOA

© **FLAME** – July 2024

